

Supplementary Material for: Measuring Ageism in Large Language Models

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1 Description of cue words for each ageism classic component.

Table 1 presents the 107 cue words used during the data collection process, categorized according to the three classic components of ageism: cognitive, affective, and behavioral.

2 Distribution of Option Selections by Large Language Models Across Academic Disciplines

To examine how large language models (LLMs) behave when processing sentences from different academic disciplines, we analyzed the proportions of option selections in both intrasentence and intersentence tasks. For each task type, two prompt settings were considered: a default prompt and an anti-stereotype prompt. The academic disciplines include Arts, Economics, Engineering, Law, Literature, Management, and Science. Figures 1–4 illustrate the distribution of the four option types—Stereotypical (S), Anti-stereotypical (ATS), Neutral (N), and Unrelated (U)—selected by six LLMs across academic disciplines.

3 Distribution of Option Selections by Large Language Models Across Genders

To examine how large language models (LLMs) behave when processing sentences authored by participants of different genders, we analyzed the proportions of option selections in both intrasentence and intersentence tasks. For each task type, two prompt settings were considered: a default prompt and an anti-stereotype prompt. Tables 2, 3, and 4 report the distribution of the four option types—Stereotypical (S), Anti-stereotypical (ATS), Neutral (N), and Unrelated (U)—as well as the corresponding LMS, AS, and ITS scores, selected or generated by six LLMs when handling gender-differentiated inputs.

4 Distribution of Option Selections by Large Language Models Across Ageism Components

To investigate how large language models (LLMs) respond to different types of ageism, we analyzed the distribution of option selections across the three classic components of ageism: cognitive, affective, and behavioral. For both the intrasentence and intersentence tasks, we compared the selection rates of four option types under the default

and anti-stereotype prompt settings. Figure 5 presents the heatmap of option distributions for the intrasentence task, while Figure 6 shows the corresponding results for the intersentence task. Table 5 reports the LMS, AS, and ITS scores of the models when handling content associated with each ageism component.

5 AgeismSet Collection Task Screenshots

Figures 7–8 respectively show screenshots of the data collection interfaces for intrasentence and intersentence tasks (The original Chinese interface text has been translated into English).

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Table 1. Cue words categorized according to the three classic components of ageism: cognitive, affective, and behavioral.

Component	Cue Words
Cognitive	Intelligence, Memory, Attention, Thinking patterns, Self-awareness, Environmental awareness, Wisdom and insight, Learning ability, Execution ability, Cognitive ability, Interests, Creativity, Lifestyle habits, Rights, Cultural level, Life experience, Worldview, Values, Life beliefs, Safety awareness, Retirement planning, Social relationships, Expressive ability
Affective	Adaptability, Popularity, Sense of belonging, Sense of identity, Loneliness, Satisfaction, Trust, Emotions, Family relationships, Team spirit, Self-confidence, Sense of responsibility, Curiosity, Stress, Conservativeness, Self-esteem, Mental health, Mental illness, Social status, Traditional customs, Quality of life, Attitude towards life, Spirit, Temperament, Work attitude
Behavioral	Physical condition, Physical fitness, Chronic diseases, Medical care, Illness, Activity level, Exercise, Mobility, Diet, Sleep, Daily life, Travel, Hospitals, Nursing homes, Food markets, Buses, Food delivery, Subways, High-speed trains, Economic conditions, Social security, Welfare subsidies, Legal protection, Rights protection, Social justice, Shopping consumption, Family care, Housework, Social activities, Social networks, Social skills, Social tools, Parks, Home, Community, Mobile phones, Cultural heritage, Lifestyle, Health preservation, Health care, Entertainment, Tourism, Literature, Art, Handicrafts, Reading, Leisure, Living environment, Behavior, Work efficiency, Work environment, Profession, Skills, New technologies, Training, Professional qualities, Television, Cinemas, Express delivery

Figure 1. Distribution of option selections across academic disciplines under the default prompt (intrasentence task).

Figure 2. Distribution of option selections across academic disciplines under the default prompt (intersentence task).

Figure 3. Distribution of option selections across academic disciplines under the anti-stereotype prompt (intrasentence task).

Figure 4. Distribution of option selections across academic disciplines under the anti-stereotype prompt (intersentence task).

Table 2. Option selection distribution by large language models in the intrasentence task for sentences authored by participants of different genders.

Option	GPT-4	GPT-3.5	GLM-3-Turbo	ERNIE Bot	Gemini Pro	DeepSeek-V3
Default prompt – Male						
S (Stereotypical)	58.20	52.86	55.71	50.85	57.40	59.57
ATS (Anti-stereotypical)	16.82	23.57	19.15	22.11	16.78	16.98
N (Neutral)	21.10	18.83	22.38	23.96	22.11	20.82
U (Unrelated)	3.88	4.74	2.76	3.08	3.71	2.63
Default prompt – Female						
S (Stereotypical)	56.00	52.21	55.69	52.07	57.30	57.73
ATS (Anti-stereotypical)	17.60	23.96	18.34	19.95	17.13	18.67
N (Neutral)	22.93	19.01	22.89	25.30	22.89	20.93
U (Unrelated)	3.47	4.82	3.08	2.68	2.68	2.67
Anti-stereotype prompt – Male						
S (Stereotypical)	46.11	51.02	51.14	40.92	37.85	53.53
ATS (Anti-stereotypical)	22.03	17.31	20.08	25.02	17.32	17.65
N (Neutral)	28.40	28.73	25.29	30.19	40.61	26.04
U (Unrelated)	3.46	2.94	3.49	3.87	4.22	2.78
Anti-stereotype prompt – Female						
S (Stereotypical)	45.06	49.33	51.54	39.68	33.60	52.00
ATS (Anti-stereotypical)	20.72	17.73	19.89	22.39	14.45	19.47
N (Neutral)	31.55	29.87	25.23	33.24	47.26	24.80
U (Unrelated)	2.67	3.07	3.34	4.69	4.69	3.73

Table 3. Option selection distribution by large language models in the intersentence task for sentences authored by participants of different genders.

Option	GPT-4	GPT-3.5	GLM-3-Turbo	ERNIE Bot	Gemini Pro	DeepSeek-V3
Default prompt – Male						
S (Stereotypical)	51.61	43.58	43.34	42.34	45.53	50.00
ATS (Anti-stereotypical)	17.36	26.08	21.81	24.38	20.32	19.01
N (Neutral)	23.10	24.63	28.06	27.52	28.81	26.49
U (Unrelated)	7.93	5.71	6.79	5.76	5.34	4.50
Default prompt – Female						
S (Stereotypical)	57.73	45.86	47.99	45.59	47.86	53.60
ATS (Anti-stereotypical)	16.00	26.34	22.19	25.00	17.92	19.33
N (Neutral)	19.07	23.66	24.87	23.26	27.54	22.27
U (Unrelated)	7.20	4.14	4.95	6.15	6.68	4.80
Anti-stereotype prompt – Male						
S (Stereotypical)	38.81	39.99	39.76	33.99	24.72	39.79
ATS (Anti-stereotypical)	23.38	18.33	21.64	27.31	17.46	21.32
N (Neutral)	31.51	35.81	32.44	32.98	50.60	33.93
U (Unrelated)	6.30	5.87	6.16	5.72	7.22	4.96
Anti-stereotype prompt – Female						
S (Stereotypical)	38.10	42.45	42.51	34.01	24.46	40.40
ATS (Anti-stereotypical)	24.47	17.36	22.73	28.44	18.72	22.40
N (Neutral)	31.95	34.05	29.81	31.97	49.47	31.87
U (Unrelated)	5.48	6.14	4.95	5.58	7.35	5.33

Table 4. LMS, AS, and ITS scores of large language models in the intrasentence and intersentence tasks for sentences authored by participants of different genders.

Model	Intrasentence task			Intersentence task		
	LMS	AS	ITS	LMS	AS	ITS
Default prompt – Male						
GPT-4	96.12	39.86	38.31	92.07	44.42	40.90
GPT-3.5	95.26	44.77	42.65	94.29	53.56	50.51
GLM-3-Turbo	97.24	42.92	41.73	93.21	53.26	49.65
ERNIE Bot	96.92	47.61	46.14	94.25	54.78	51.63
Gemini Pro	96.29	40.74	39.23	94.66	51.80	49.03
DeepSeek-V3	97.37	39.12	38.09	95.50	47.75	45.60
Default prompt – Female						
GPT-4	96.53	42.26	40.80	92.80	38.67	35.89
GPT-3.5	95.18	45.38	43.19	95.86	52.07	49.91
GLM-3-Turbo	96.92	42.77	41.45	95.05	49.54	47.08
ERNIE Bot	97.32	46.59	45.34	93.85	51.34	48.18
Gemini Pro	97.32	41.36	40.26	93.32	48.80	45.54
DeepSeek-V3	97.33	40.94	39.84	95.20	44.00	41.89
Anti-stereotype prompt – Male						
GPT-4	96.54	52.16	50.36	93.70	58.04	54.38
GPT-3.5	97.06	47.51	46.11	94.13	57.07	53.72
GLM-3-Turbo	96.51	47.12	45.47	93.84	57.16	53.64
ERNIE Bot	96.13	57.14	54.93	94.28	63.14	59.53
Gemini Pro	95.78	60.04	57.51	92.78	71.67	66.50
DeepSeek-V3	97.22	45.08	43.83	95.04	57.73	54.87
Anti-stereotype prompt – Female						
GPT-4	97.33	53.61	52.18	94.52	59.16	55.92
GPT-3.5	96.93	49.14	47.63	93.86	54.48	51.13
GLM-3-Turbo	96.66	46.79	45.23	95.05	55.02	52.29
ERNIE Bot	95.31	57.98	55.26	94.42	63.20	59.67
Gemini Pro	95.31	64.06	61.06	92.65	71.86	66.58
DeepSeek-V3	96.27	46.14	44.41	94.67	56.94	53.90

Figure 5. Option selection distribution by large language models in the intrasentence task, across ageism components and prompt types.

Figure 6. Option selection distribution by large language models in the intersentence task, across ageism components and prompt types.

Table 5. LMS, AS, and ITS scores for each model in the intrasentence and intersentence tasks, grouped by ageism component.

Model	Intrasentence task			Intersentence task		
	LMS	AS	ITS	LMS	AS	ITS
Default prompt – Cognitive						
GPT-4	97.40	40.75	39.69	91.95	43.92	40.38
GPT-3.5	94.93	46.24	43.89	95.54	55.75	53.26
GLM-3-Turbo	97.54	43.34	42.27	94.51	55.06	52.03
ERNIE Bot	96.82	50.36	48.76	94.00	55.49	52.16
Gemini Pro	96.67	41.90	40.50	94.68	52.91	50.10
DeepSeek-V3	97.40	38.87	37.86	95.21	48.63	46.30
Default prompt – Affective						
GPT-4	95.17	43.51	41.41	93.17	45.16	42.08
GPT-3.5	95.41	47.39	45.21	95.61	53.68	51.32
GLM-3-Turbo	97.20	47.26	45.94	93.81	52.77	49.50
ERNIE Bot	96.94	48.15	46.68	94.71	55.68	52.73
Gemini Pro	96.43	42.30	40.79	94.32	53.29	50.26
DeepSeek-V3	97.20	41.98	40.81	96.13	49.48	47.57
Default prompt – Behavioral						
GPT-4	96.25	39.20	37.73	91.85	42.22	38.77
GPT-3.5	95.25	43.53	41.46	93.86	52.62	49.39
GLM-3-Turbo	97.06	41.04	39.83	93.36	51.63	48.20
ERNIE Bot	97.17	46.30	44.98	93.98	52.96	49.77
Gemini Pro	96.55	40.06	38.67	94.14	49.94	47.02
DeepSeek-V3	97.43	38.78	37.78	95.17	45.28	43.09
Anti-stereotype prompt – Cognitive						
GPT-4	95.94	59.85	57.42	93.66	65.16	61.02
GPT-3.5	96.09	51.44	49.43	93.48	62.26	58.20
GLM-3-Turbo	96.68	50.07	48.41	93.83	59.00	55.36
ERNIE Bot	95.37	65.56	62.52	94.22	65.24	61.47
Gemini Pro	95.80	67.66	64.81	92.45	73.76	68.19
DeepSeek-V3	97.54	47.76	46.59	94.18	61.13	57.57
Anti-stereotype prompt – Affective						
GPT-4	96.43	50.70	48.89	94.58	59.36	56.14
GPT-3.5	97.46	48.09	46.87	95.23	59.08	56.27
GLM-3-Turbo	96.56	50.19	48.46	95.10	57.29	54.48
ERNIE Bot	95.79	56.19	53.82	95.41	63.24	60.33
Gemini Pro	95.54	57.52	54.95	93.93	71.52	67.17
DeepSeek-V3	97.46	47.08	45.88	95.75	59.86	57.31
Anti-stereotype prompt – Behavioral						
GPT-4	97.14	50.92	49.47	93.57	56.16	52.54
GPT-3.5	97.20	46.86	45.55	93.64	53.74	50.32
GLM-3-Turbo	96.42	44.79	43.19	93.75	56.08	52.57
ERNIE Bot	96.21	55.28	53.19	93.94	61.98	58.22
Gemini Pro	95.65	60.36	57.74	92.33	71.56	66.07
DeepSeek-V3	96.53	43.82	42.29	94.78	55.59	52.69

Task One:

Please write an incomplete sentence related to the elderly and containing the target word "XX" (or a description synonymous with the target word). The sentence should be neutral but missing a word to be filled in (replaced by ellipsis ...).

Then generate the following four types of candidate words for the sentence, all of which can form semantically complete and coherent sentences when filled in:

- (1) Stereotypical words (supporting stereotypes about the target word)
- (2) Anti-stereotypical words (reasonable in the real world, eliminating stereotypes about the target word)
- (3) Neutral words (without stereotypes or anti-stereotypes)
- (4) Unrelated words (maintaining the same part of speech as the above three words (e.g., nouns, verbs, adjectives), but unrelated to the preceding context)

* 1. Cue word: Physical condition

Please write a sentence related to the elderly, with the missing part represented by "..."

stereotype

anti-stereotype

neutral impression

unrelated option

	<input type="text"/>

Figure 7. Data Collection Interface for Intrasentence Task

Task Two:

Based on the theme "elderly" and target word "XX," write a neutral incomplete sentence for the second half (represented by "..."). Then, generate the following four types of completion for the sentence:

Stereotypical sentence (supports stereotypes about the target)

Anti-stereotypical sentence (reasonable in the real world and eliminates stereotypes about the target)

Neutral sentence (without stereotypes or anti-stereotypes)

Unrelated sentence (maintains the same sentence structure as the above three sentences, coherent, but unrelated to the preceding context. The additional sentence should have a complete subject-verb-object structure.)

* 1. Cue word: Physical fitness

Please write a neutral sentence related to the elderly.	<input type="text"/>
Stereotypical sentence	<input type="text"/>
Anti-stereotypical sentence	<input type="text"/>
Neutral sentence	<input type="text"/>
Unrelated sentence	<input type="text"/>

Figure 8. Data Collection Interface for Intersentence Task